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A Comparative Study of Art History Education Paradigms in China and the United States

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Abstract

Art education in China and the United States has both differences and similarities. Both systems distinguish between practice-oriented art creation education and theory-oriented art history and theory education. Previous studies have focused extensively on the practical aspects of art education in China and the United States, often overlooking comparative research on the models and practical approaches of art history education. This article conducts a comparative study of art history education in China and the United States, focusing on aspects such as curriculum design, training programs, faculty allocation, and teaching methods. Through this analysis, the study aims to derive meaningful academic insights, identify practical pathways, and propose reform strategies, thereby offering inspiration for addressing existing issues and improving art history education in both countries.

Key Words

Art history education, discipline system, curriculum design, training methods

Art history education in the United States spans various education levels, including universities, colleges, and primary and secondary schools. Many institutions offer a wide range of art history courses, covering diverse periods from ancient to contemporary art history. These courses are typically designed to develop students' understanding and analytical skills in art, encouraging them to identify connections and trends across art from different cultures and periods. As Charles Eliot Norton (1827-1908) suggested in his teaching of art history at Harvard University, the goal of art history education is to make students aware of the noble life and pure ways of thinking that underlie all forms of human artistic expression, including poetry, painting, sculpture, and architecture.¹ Art history education in China also spans various stages of learning; however, since academic-based art history education started relatively late, and due to differences in the educational system and art history education models compared to the United States, there are significant differences between Chinese and American art history education in terms of teaching methods, curriculum design, and educational structure.

1. Similarities and Differences in the Disciplinary System of Art History Education between China and the United States

China and the United States have different understandings about the position of art history education within the overall academic system. In China, art history programs are often housed within the department of art history (or department of fine arts history) at art institutions. For example, the Department of Art History at the Central Academy of Fine Arts is part of its humanities college, a secondary-level college, and other specialized art schools, such as the China Academy of Art, also have art history departments which are similarly affiliated with secondary-level colleges. In Chinese comprehensive universities, art history departments are typically located within the art colleges (or colleges of fine arts). In contrast, in the United States, art history is often part of the broader liberal arts framework. For example, Harvard offers graduate programs in art history and architecture through a dedicated Department of History of Art and Architecture, which is affiliated with the Graduate School

Figure 1. The Auguste Rodin (1840-1917) sculpture in front of the Museum Square at Stanford University.

of Arts and Sciences. Princeton University also offers graduate programs in art and archaeology, which are housed within the Department of Art and Archaeology.

At Columbia University, art history and archaeology fall under the Graduate School of Arts and Sciences. The University of Chicago has a dedicated Department of Art

History. At the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT), art history and theory are part of the School of Architecture and Planning. At the University of California, Berkeley (UC Berkeley), art history is within the College of Letters and Science, and at the University of California, Davis (UC Davis), art history is also part of the College of Letters and Science. It is clear that there are significant differences in the way art history is positioned within the academic systems of China and the United States. In the United States, art history is regarded as a mature and independent academic discipline, equivalent to a first-level discipline in China. In contrast, art history in China is typically considered a sub-discipline under the first-level discipline of arts studies. Art history in China has not only failed to establish itself as an independent discipline, but it has also become a subordinate field to artistic creation. Many comprehensive universities do not have art history departments in their art colleges and, even in some institutions, art history courses may not be fully offered. Of course, in the United States art history is also sometimes housed within art departments. For example, at Wayne State University the Department of Art History is part of the College of Fine, Performing, and Communication Arts, and at the University of South Florida the Department of Art History is situated within the College of The Arts.

It is important to emphasize that in the United States, art history is highly valued even at the pre-college stage. In the advanced placement (AP) exams, there is a dedicated art history subject, and this discipline has become an important measure of a student's artistic literacy when universities assess applicants for admission. It is clear that as a humanities discipline, art history is far more valued in the United States than in China. As a foundational field within the humanities, art history has already highlighted its significance and value in the US academic system.

2. Similarities and Differences in the Curriculum of Art History in China and the United States

“By the 1990s, many universities in the United States had established departments of art history, offering master's degree programs in art history. Several universities also launched Ph.D. programs in art history. The United States has become the country that trains the largest number of high-level art history professionals in the world today.”² There is a significant difference in the curriculum of art history between China and the United States, particularly in the proportion of course content. From the AP art history syllabus in the United States it

is clear that the course adopts a global perspective on art history. While based on the European tradition of art history, it comprehensively covers art and culture from around the world. For example, it includes detailed introductions to Chinese classical art history resources, such as the Terracotta Army, cave art, the Song Dynasty's *Travelers in the Mountains and Streams* by Fan Kuan, and the architecture of the Forbidden City. Additionally, contemporary art is also covered, with discussions of artists such as Cai Guo-Qiang and Xu Bing. The curriculum of art history education in the United States typically covers a broad range of periods and themes to provide a comprehensive learning experience. Students may study various periods such as ancient, Renaissance, modern, and more, while focusing on different forms of art, including painting, sculpture, architecture, photography, and others. The courses may also include interdisciplinary content, addressing fields such as literature, philosophy, and history, to help students better understand the relationship between art, society, and culture. The educational goals typically include cultivating students' critical thinking, research skills, and cross-cultural understanding.

For example, Harvard's art history curriculum is very comprehensive, designed to cover a wide range of disciplinary content and to cultivate students' critical thinking and cultural understanding skills. Specific courses at Harvard might include: 1) Introduction to Art History — Provides a comprehensive overview of key periods and movements in art history, including ancient art, the Renaissance, Modernism, and more; 2) Global Art History — Examines artistic traditions from around the world, covering the art developments in regions such as Asia, Africa, and Latin America; 3) Contemporary Art Theory — Explores theoretical frameworks, critical methods, and the response of contemporary art to societal and cultural changes; 4) Museum Studies and Curating — Focuses on the fundamental principles of museum studies, equipping students with professional skills in curating and exhibition design; 5) Interdisciplinary Studies — Offers students the opportunity to integrate other disciplines, such as history, literature, and philosophy, to deeply investigate the intersection of art and culture; 6) Art and Society — Focuses on the relationship between art and society, politics, and culture, providing an in-depth understanding of the role of art in social transformation.

These course designs reflect Harvard's commitment to cultivating students with a broad knowledge base and deep professional skills. Students have the opportunity to delve into the field of art through these courses and engage in academic discussions within various cultural,

historical, and theoretical frameworks. At UC Berkeley the art history curriculum, influenced by scholars such as James Cahill (1926-2014), places a strong emphasis on Asian art with a focus on the development of art across Asia, including the traditional and modern art of regions such as China, Japan, and India. It also pays significant attention to modern and contemporary art, exploring artistic movements, practices, and theories from the twentieth century onwards, such as Modernism, Abstract Expressionism, and Postmodernism. The curriculum further explores museums and collections, examining the fundamental principles of museum studies, art collections, and curating, and aims to develop students' skills for working in museums and art institutions. In the field of digital art and media studies, the program also gives considerable attention to the forms of artistic expression in the digital age, including virtual reality and digital art. The University of Kansas' School of the Arts is another world-renowned institution for the study of East Asian art. In the spring semester of 2024, among the twenty courses offered, the school set up nine courses closely related to East Asian art, including Visual Arts of East Asia, Japanese Sculpture, Manga (Japanese Comics)—History and Theory, Japanese Woodblock Prints, Modern Korean Art and Culture, Japanese Art and Culture, Korean Popular Music and its Art, Korean Art Seminar—Korean Architecture, and Japanese Art Seminar – Cross-Cultural Communication in Japanese Art. At UC Davis, the art history curriculum is designed around the research interests of the faculty. For example, Professor Katharine P. Burnett, who specializes in Chinese art history and tea culture, offers courses such as *The Art History of Tea Ceramics* and *Art History Research and Writing Methods*. In order to introduce Chinese tea culture to more Western scholars, faculty, and students, Burnett established the Global Tea Institute for the Study of Tea Culture and Science. She brings her personal collection of Chinese and Japanese tea utensils to the classroom and provides each student with a tea cup, allowing them to enjoy traditional Chinese Kungfu Tea while attending class. This course combines academic research with a sensory cultural experience, making it one of the most unique courses in art history departments in the United States. In addition, Burnett has organized large-scale seminars, such as the *9th Annual GTI Colloquium: Tea in a Changing World* (January 25, 2024), and curated the *Heaven and Earth in a Small Teapot* exhibition (January 26, 2024 — March 22, 2024) at the university's Special Collections. She invites renowned global tea culture experts to give lectures to faculty and students, using exhibitions to promote East Asian tea culture. Beyond the classroom, Burnett has

opened new methods and experiences for studying art history, providing a unique platform for faculty and students to engage with both academic research and cultural exploration. This integrated model of art history education, which combines courses, conferences, exhibitions, and immersive cultural experiences, resonates with the multidimensional, globalized, specialized, and detailed approach of contemporary education. It also serves as an exemplary contribution to art history education in higher education institutions across the United States and globally. UC Davis Professor Tallinn Grigor, for example, offers courses such as *Modern and Contemporary Global Architecture* and *Art and Critical and (Post) Colonial Theory*. Other UC Davis faculty members, based on their own research interests, have developed specialized courses in areas such as Mediterranean art and Central Asian art.

Art history in Chinese higher education typically covers a rich and in-depth curriculum. These courses aim to promote a comprehensive understanding of both traditional and modern Chinese art. Typical art history courses may include the following areas: Firstly, ancient Chinese art history focuses on the study of ancient art forms such as painting, sculpture, and architecture, with an emphasis on their historical, cultural, and religious contexts. Secondly, modern and contemporary Chinese art history examines the development of art since the late nineteenth century, including modern and contemporary painting, sculpture, photography, and other art forms, with a focus on the influence of social and political transformations on art. Thirdly, traditional scholar's studio arts focuses on Chinese cultural traditions related to scholar's studio tools, seal carving, calligraphy, and other art forms, emphasizing aesthetic concepts and artistic techniques. Finally, art theory and criticism primarily explores art theories and critical methodologies, aiming to cultivate students' critical thinking and analytical skills. Moreover, cultural heritage and conservation focuses on the protection, restoration, and management of cultural heritage, aiming to cultivate students' sense of responsibility and professional skills in artifact preservation. China's art history curriculum aims to preserve and promote Chinese culture while integrating traditional art into the modern social context, with the goal of fostering students' deep understanding of art and independent thinking skills. There are differences in the curriculum design of art history education between China and the United States. In China, art history education often places more emphasis on traditional art and culture, including ancient Chinese painting, sculpture, and other forms. The courses may also focus more on the transmission of traditional values and

Figure 2. Art history literature in the library collection of the University of California, Davis.

aesthetic concepts.

The foreign art history curriculum in Chinese art academies is typically designed to be comprehensive, aiming to foster a deep understanding of the development of world art. The curriculum generally includes the following topics: Firstly, introduction to Western art history focuses on key periods such as Ancient Greece and Rome, the Renaissance, Baroque, and Modernism, introducing the major stages of Western art development. The course examines how art evolved through these periods, highlighting the cultural, intellectual, and social contexts that influenced artistic creation in the Western world. Secondly, Asian art history examines the traditional art of various Asian regions, including East Asia and South Asia. This course covers the art forms of countries such as China, Japan, and India, focusing on their painting, sculpture, architecture, and other artistic expressions, while exploring the cultural, religious, and historical contexts that shaped these artistic traditions. Thirdly, African and Oceanic art focuses on the indigenous and tribal art of Africa and Oceania, as well as modern and contemporary art from these regions. The course explores the traditional art forms, such as masks, sculptures, and textiles, as well as how these regions have contributed to global art movements in the modern

and contemporary periods. It also examines the impact of colonization, cultural exchange, and globalization on the development of art in these areas. Fourthly, Latin American art explores movements such as Mexican Muralism and Latin American Modernism, examining the unique artistic development of the region. The course delves into the historical, social, and political contexts that shaped the art of Latin America, highlighting key figures and movements that responded to issues such as identity, revolution, and post-colonialism, and their influence on global art history. Finally, contemporary global art focuses on current global art phenomena, including international exhibitions, cross-cultural art exchanges, and the exploration of contemporary art trends. This course aims to cultivate students' insights into the evolving directions of contemporary art. Through these foreign art history courses, students are able to broaden their perspectives, understand artistic expressions within different cultural contexts, and foster cross-cultural understanding while engaging with global art movements and phenomena. In contrast, art history courses in the United States tend to offer a broader perspective, encompassing art from different cultures and periods around the world. These courses often place greater emphasis on cross-cultural comparison and critical thinking, highlighting students' understanding

of multiculturalism. Additionally, courses in the United States may be more flexible, allowing students to choose specific periods or themes for in-depth study, enabling them to tailor their education according to their academic interests and research goals.

3. Similarities and Differences in the Approaches to Art History Education in China and the United States

There are significant differences in the approaches to art history education between China and the United States. In the United States, art history education focuses on developing students' critical thinking and independent research skills, with an emphasis on understanding diverse cultures and artistic styles from different historical periods. In contrast, China's traditional focus has been more on the transmission of foundational knowledge, emphasizing students' understanding and inheritance of Chinese traditional art. These differences are shaped by the distinct cultural and educational systems in each country.

There are also differences in teaching methods between China and the United States, particularly regarding classroom interaction, group discussions, field trips, and research projects. Both countries offer large and small classes in art history education. Large classes are often general courses open to many students across different disciplines and are typically taught using PowerPoint (PPT) presentations and Q&A sessions. In contrast, small classes in the United States primarily use a discussion-based approach, which is a distinctive feature of American education. As noted, "America's cultural (core) courses cover literature, philosophy, social sciences, and natural sciences, which provide students with a deep humanistic foundation. Design students, for instance, are required to take more courses in the humanities."³ Regardless of whether it's a large or small class, the way in which students and instructors interact in the classroom differs greatly between China and the United States. American classrooms often adopt an inquiry-based and question-driven approach, encouraging active discussion of students' doubts about art history, which largely achieves the goals of art history education. The teaching style in American classrooms is typically open and interactive, emphasizing student participation and critical thinking. One notable feature of art history courses in the United States is that students are not required to have a background in art history. Students from various disciplines, such as history, literature, philosophy, religious studies (ancient or modern), political science, economics, music, mathematics, and others are welcome to enroll. As long as students have

an interest in visual arts and historical research, they are encouraged to join art history classes. Professors particularly value the diverse perspectives and insights that students from different academic backgrounds bring to the classroom. The characteristics of art history classroom discussions in the United States include high student engagement, open-ended questions as the basis for discussions, an emphasis on diverse viewpoints and cultural contexts in art criticism, the cultivation of critical thinking skills to encourage students to think analytically and question deeply, and the fact that students do not need to have a background in art history. Overall, the discussion approach in American classrooms reflects values that support student participation, critical thinking, and diversity, aiming to develop students' comprehensive abilities in both academic and societal contexts. In contrast, Chinese art history education typically follows a more traditional format where the teacher lectures and students listen, with little or no emphasis on discussion or interaction. This format often lacks in-depth discussions of key issues in art history, and critical questions in the field are not explored thoroughly. As a result, there is a missed opportunity for students to engage deeply with contentious or unclear aspects of art history, hindering the development of their critical thinking and analytical skills in the subject.

Art history education in the United States typically fosters students' critical thinking and independent research skills through the following methods.

The first method is discussion and debate. In each class, instructors encourage students to participate in discussions and debates according to the course structure, prompting them to think deeply about artworks and their historical context, and view issues from multiple perspectives. For example, when discussing an ancient Chinese painting, the instructor may ask the following questions to stimulate discussion: Who is the artist, and what is the historical period of the work? What is the content depicted in the painting? What was the artistic intention behind its creation? What was the functional purpose of the painting? How does this painting compare to similar (or contemporaneous) works? Why did this style emerge, and what was its impact? How might the viewers' perception of this artwork differ between the time it was created and today? Although each instructor may phrase their questions differently, they all center around the same core issue: Why did this artwork appear in its particular form within a specific historical and cultural context? Students conduct systematic research and review relevant literature to explore these questions and present their own views. The instructor's role is to guide the process, while most of the material and

assignments are selected and deeply explored by the students based on their own interests. The instructor provides encouragement and feedback. Even if students present views that contradict authoritative interpretations, as long as their arguments are coherent and supported by appropriate evidence, the instructor fully supports them and may even recommend their work for publication.

The second method is writing papers. The core component of American art history education lies in paper writing, particularly critical writing. Art history courses typically require students to engage in critical writing, analyzing and evaluating artworks while attempting to connect them with contemporary academic perspectives. This helps to cultivate students' writing and argumentative skills. Students are expected not only to understand art, but also to be familiar with history, literature, and philosophy, among other disciplines. More importantly, students should master how to express their views in the most concise language and with analytical structure. Students are required to have a broad perspective on art history, along with the precise writing ability of a literary scholar, the rigor of a lawyer's argumentation, and the free imagination of an artist. It can be said that the study of art history is based on strong writing and argumentative skills. Many graduate students and PhD candidates in art history have solid English writing abilities, often having a background in literature. Therefore, many top universities in the United States offer writing courses or courses focused on analyzing historical materials (historiography on art history). For example, Professor Tao Yoting at UC Davis offers courses on writing art history paper abstracts for both undergraduate and graduate students. Her course is centered around the XYZ paper model, where each student chooses a topic they like or are familiar with and then summarizes their research according to the XYZ structure. X represents the current research question and status, Y represents the new methods or materials used, and Z represents the conclusions or the root causes of the problem solved. In class, she engages in about fifteen minutes of discussion for each student's chosen topic, during which all students and visiting scholars are invited to give feedback. After a period of training, students develop a specific research model and quickly master the core skills of paper writing. This approach lays the foundation for later stages of thesis proposal, writing, and defense. It effectively addresses the common challenges students face when selecting topics in the early stages of writing an art history paper.

American art history education also places a strong emphasis on training students in public speaking. As

art history scholars, students are tasked with learning how to explain the characteristics, development, and impact of artworks to a non-specialist audience, including society, the community, and non-art history professionals at school. Each graduate student is required to give a twenty- to thirty-minute presentation at the end of the semester, presenting their paper and answering questions. This requires students to practice their presentation repeatedly in advance to ensure they can finish within the time frame, while also preparing a corresponding PPT. The PPT should be concise, with high-quality images of the artworks, and each image must be labeled with the artwork's name, artist, creation date, materials, dimensions, and the institution where the work is housed. This means students need to contact the institution in advance to obtain permission and authorization for the public display of these images. The PPT should not have too many slides, as that would make it difficult for the audience to read in detail, nor should it have too few slides, as this could make the presentation feel too sparse. After the presentation, students must accept feedback and answer questions from both the instructor and fellow students. Typically, the questions are friendly and constructive, and students are encouraged to answer according to their own understanding. Finally, the instructor will summarize the presentation and provide written feedback within a week. These evaluations are mostly positive, but also include deeper questions and discussions, with the aim of encouraging students to revise or strengthen their arguments in the final paper. A paper of fifteen to twenty pages goes through several stages: attending class, formulating a topic, gathering materials, selecting references, writing the paper, self-editing, delivering the presentation, receiving oral suggestions from peers and instructors, receiving written feedback from the instructor, and revising the paper based on that feedback. This entire process, which occurs over the course of three to four months, plays a crucial role in enhancing students' overall abilities and academic habits.

Third, in the United States students have a wide variety of options for pursuing art history research, with different levels of courses available. Some courses are lower-division classes aimed at undergraduate students, while others are upper-division courses for graduate students or doctoral candidates. There are also seminars for advanced graduate students, as well as honors programs designed for students with outstanding academic performance, intellectual abilities, and research potential. These different teaching formats naturally lead to many interdisciplinary approaches. The inherent structure of the art history education system

in the United States is not constrained by the service-oriented nature of art creation disciplines which allows for greater encouragement of interdisciplinary learning. This enables students to integrate art history with other fields such as philosophy, history, literature, and more, thus broadening their intellectual horizons. Moreover, the range of topics in American art history research is vast. Students' focus is not limited to painting, sculpture, and architecture. In fact, any material related to the artistic life can be a subject of study, such as teapots, ceramics, jewelry, wallpaper, gardens, gravestones, churches, temples, coins, posters, comics, murals, graffiti, fans, books, illustrated manuscripts, popular culture, museum design, and exhibition curation.

Fourth, students in the United States have the opportunity to visit art museums, galleries, and other cultural institutions for field trips, allowing them to experience artworks firsthand and develop independent insights. For example, in the summer of 2023, Professor Wang Zhonghua from Princeton led her doctoral students to London, where they visited the British Museum's exhibition *China's Hidden Century: A Century of Subdued Glory*. They also recently visited the Cleveland Museum of Art's exhibition *China's Southern Paradise: Treasures from the Lower Yangzi Delta*. After viewing the Cleveland exhibition, Wang's student Zhuolun Xie noted that the exhibition not only taught the students about the various interpretations of Jiangnan culture by Chinese artists throughout history, but also helped them appreciate the region's central role in cross-cultural artistic exchanges. By studying and comparing works such as Dong Qichang's landscape handscroll *Autumn Clearing over the Mountains* and portraits of Dong, Zhuolun Xie was able to imagine, from a "vivid and dynamic" perspective, Dong's significant position within the late Ming Jiangnan art circle.

Fifth, universities in the United States have rich collections of both physical and digital resources, which provide important materials for the teaching and research of art history. Many universities in the United States have East Asian libraries, which offer abundant physical resources for the study of Chinese art history. For books not available in the university's collection, students can request them through interlibrary loan (ILL), a system where libraries from all universities, museums, and research institutions in the United States share their collections. Books borrowed through ILL usually arrive within one to two weeks. If a book cannot be borrowed (e.g., due to its high demand for research, poor condition, or its value as a rare resource), the university may purchase it for the student's research. For some rare editions, such as Kolor prints from the Republican era,

rare ancient texts, or large art catalogs, students can search for them on WorldCat and obtain them through ILL. Many Kolor prints and ancient texts have already been digitized, and students can access them online through the university's digital library, HathiTrust, simply by logging into their library accounts;—they can even download the materials they need. In addition, university libraries provide powerful digital resources. Journals, papers, reviews, and some books published online are available in PDF format for download through the library's website. Some top universities also offer extensive online resources for East Asian studies, languages, and literature. For example, the University of California library system offers online collections related to Chinese, Japanese, and Korean culture and history. By logging into the library system, students can access databases such as the China Journal Full-Text Database, Digital Journal Database, Chinese PhD and Master's Theses Database, National Philosophy and Social Science Academic Journal Database, Renmin University Newspaper Clipping Service, Taiwan Electronic Journals Service Network, National Newspaper Index, Joint Knowledge Base, People's Daily e-version, Shen Bao, Wenyan Pavilion Siku Quanshu, Chinese Historical Texts Database, Ancient and Modern Books Integrated Collection (Punctuation), Taiwan Literary Series, Chinese Local Gazetteers, Basic Ancient Chinese Books Database, Da Cheng Old Periodicals Full-Text Database, and the Republican Periodicals Full-Text Database (1911-1949). These precious materials can all be freely accessed through the library's website and are crucial references and resources for art history studies.

In addition, universities in the United States often offer research projects as part of art history education. These projects are typically provided for free, and some even offer stipends, though the competition for them is intense. Students must apply and undergo interviews to be selected for these projects. The application requires a personal statement of about 500 words, a resumé, and one to three recommendation letters. The personal statement should clearly explain how the project aligns with the student's research interests and what improvements or advancements they expect to gain from participating. Once selected for an interview, candidates must meet with at least three experts for discussions. Participating in these research projects helps students expand their opportunities for hands-on experience, enhances their ability to search for, analyze, and synthesize information, improves their English writing and speaking skills, and allows them to learn about the latest research from professors, experts, and PhD students from other universities through these platforms. For example, the

University of Michigan, with its strong collection of Chinese artworks, established the Chinese Object Study Program in 2024. This program was created and is operated by the Smithsonian National Museum of Asian Art, with funding from the Mellon Foundation. It is co-hosted by renowned art historians from the University of Michigan Museum of Art (UMMA), including Oyobe Natsu, Jonathan Hay from New York University, and Jan Stuart from the National Museum of Asian Art. The program will provide opportunities for PhD students studying Chinese art in North America and Europe to engage in exchange programs and have direct access to collections. The first seminar will be held in June 2025 at UMMA, focusing primarily on the museum's Chinese art collection. Subsequent seminars will be held at various museums across the United States and Canada. Each seminar will be co-led by two professors of Chinese art history and collaborating museum curators, with participation from artists, conservation experts, museum scientists, and scholars of Chinese art. Parti-

cipants in this academic environment will have the opportunity to closely examine valuable ancient calligraphy and painting works, cultivating a deeper understanding of art and the ability to think critically and independently. This program will have significant importance for nurturing the next generation of exceptional art historians, curators, and museum leaders. Thus, American art history education offers students a comprehensive view of art history from different historical periods and geographical locations, as well as a variety of academic subjects. It also provides methods for in-depth analysis and interpretation of visual, material, and textual evidence within specific cultural and historical contexts. Furthermore, it offers various flexible research formats. In summary, the unique interests and pursuits of each student can be fully supported and developed in American universities.

China's art history education has its unique characteristics. First, it places significant emphasis on traditional culture. Art history education in China at

Figure 3. Public art on the University of California, Davis campus.

primary, secondary, and university levels particularly focuses on understanding and inheriting traditional culture, with a strong emphasis on learning and preserving traditional Chinese art. For example, art history knowledge in primary and secondary schools primarily follows a system centered around traditional Chinese painting, calligraphy, and decorative arts, with some introduction of European classical art, but it rarely covers contemporary art or diverse artistic forms. In university education, the scope is relatively broader; however, there is a tendency to separate the teaching of art design history from the broader field of art history, rather than integrating it into the overall art history framework. Chinese art history education focuses on foundational knowledge. The educational system often emphasizes students' grasp of fundamental art history concepts, particularly an understanding of ancient art styles and techniques. Some institutions even continue this focus on foundational knowledge at the graduate level. Additionally, there is an emphasis on skill development, with some courses focusing on traditional painting and craft skills, enabling students to participate in actual artistic creation and deepen their experience and understanding of art from a practical perspective. In comparison, there are several current issues in Chinese art history education: 1) Lack of diverse perspectives: Chinese art history education sometimes places too much emphasis on tradition, with insufficient focus on multicultural and cross-cultural perspectives; 2) Limited interaction and practice: Some courses may focus excessively on theoretical knowledge, lacking in opportunities for student interaction and practical experience; 3) Outdated textbooks: Some textbooks may be relatively outdated, failing to reflect new trends and discoveries in the field of art; to address these issues, there is a need to continually update teaching methods, introduce more interdisciplinary elements, encourage independent thinking, and pay closer attention to the diversity of global art developments. Chinese art history education should learn from the experience of the United States and move toward more practical and diversified approaches.

4. Similarities and Differences in the Evaluation Systems of Art History Education in China and the United States

The evaluation systems of art history education in China and the United States emphasize different aspects. China may place greater emphasis on the inheritance of traditional culture and the mastery of skills, while the United States may focus more on students' creativity,

critical thinking, and independent research abilities.

Evaluation methods in art history education in the United States tend to be comprehensive, including essays, research projects, and participation. The evaluation system typically covers the following aspects: 1) Academic performance: This includes students' participation in class, their understanding of art works, and their grasp of historical contexts. These elements serve as important indicators of students' academic achievements; 2) Research and writing: Students' research abilities and writing skills are typically assessed through essays, research projects, etc., with an emphasis on in-depth analysis of art history topics; every art history course in universities in the United States requires students to complete a paper or give a related presentation; 3) Critical thinking: The evaluation focuses on students' critical thinking skills, including their ability to critique art works, understand different viewpoints, and form independent opinions on art history issues; 4) Field trips and exhibition participation: Students engage in field trips to museums and galleries, and participate in art exhibitions, helping them develop practical experience and an understanding of the art world; 5) Group discussions and teamwork: Through group discussions and collaborative projects, students' abilities to work with others and contribute to team objectives are assessed; 6) Interdisciplinary learning: This evaluates whether students can integrate art history with other disciplines, broadening their academic perspective. These evaluative aspects collectively encourage students to develop in academic, research, and practical fields, cultivating them into art history professionals with critical thinking and comprehensive skills.

In China, the assessment methods for art history education are more inclined towards exams and practical skills, with the evaluation system typically covering the following aspects: 1) Disciplinary knowledge: The mastery of basic concepts, historical contexts, and techniques of traditional Chinese art, as well as an understanding of relevant theories; 2) Skill development: The cultivation of students' practical skills in painting, sculpture, or other art forms, including both traditional and modern artistic practices; 3) Academic performance: Students' academic achievements are evaluated through exams and essays, including their understanding and application of art history theory; 4) Practical experience: Students are required to participate in field trips and hands-on creation, fostering their observation skills and practical abilities; 5) Creativity and independent thinking: The ability to think independently, offer unique insights, and demonstrate creativity in their work; 6) Team collaboration: Assessment of students' teamwork

abilities in group projects or collaborative activities; 7) Understanding of traditional culture: Examining students' understanding of Chinese traditional culture, including the inheritance and innovation of traditional art. While the Chinese art history education evaluation system emphasizes the inheritance of traditional culture, it is gradually placing more focus on students' creativity and independent thinking, aiming to cultivate well-rounded, multi-faceted artistic talents.

The commonality between art history education in China and the United States is the cultivation of independent thinking, encouraging students to gain a deep understanding and insight into artworks and historical contexts. With the continuous advancement of globalization, art history educators in both countries have recognized the importance of practical experience. They are increasingly providing students with opportunities for hands-on learning through field trips, project-based research, and other methods. Both systems also emphasize interdisciplinary learning, encouraging students to integrate art history with other fields to broaden their knowledge. Overall, the differences and similarities in evaluation systems between China and the United States are largely influenced by cultural differences and educational philosophies, but both are gradually moving towards a more comprehensive and diverse approach to assessment.

Conclusion

In conclusion, art history education in China and the United States is shaped by different cultural backgrounds and educational approaches, leading to distinct characteristics in their respective systems. In particular, there are significant differences in areas such as the curriculum structure, training programs, faculty composition, and teaching methods. Art

history education in the United States places greater emphasis on independent learning and a cross-cultural perspective, while China's art history education tends to focus more on traditional art history teaching and the inheritance of Chinese art. With the expansion of international exchange in recent years, there has been an increasing amount of collaboration between Chinese and American art history research and education. For example, a group of art historians led by Wu Hung and Martin Powers has brought cutting-edge United States art history scholarship to Peking University. Moreover, the University of Chicago has established a center in Beijing, regularly holding art history forums. Scholars attending these forums include iconography expert W. J. T. Mitchell, as well as Chinese art historians such as Zheng Yan, Zhu Qingsheng, He Xilin, and Huang Xiaofeng, who have made significant contributions to the field of Chinese art history research and education.

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中美藝術史教育範式比較研究

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摘要：中美兩國的美術教育既有區別，又有聯繫。中美兩國的美術教育體系都有以實踐為導向的美術創作教育和以理論為導向的美術史論教育之分。以往的研究廣泛關注中美兩國美術教育的實踐層面，往往忽視了對美術史教育模式和實踐方法的比較研究。本文對中美兩國的藝術史教育進行了比較研究，重點關注課程設計、培養方案、師資配置、教學方法等方面。通過分析，旨在得出有意義的學術見解，明確實踐路徑，提出改革策略，從而為解決兩國藝術史教育存在的問題和改進藝術史教育提供啟示。

關鍵詞：美術史教育；學科體系；課程設計；培訓方法